

A Simple Spring-Damper-Slider Model for Laminate Slippage

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1. Introduction

Autoclave curing is a common method for producing thermosetting composites. Heated to a high temperature, resin is polymerised irreversibly through cross-linking, which generates heats. Non-uniform temperature gradients and different material property of resin and fibre, lead to material straining and stresses. When built into composites, these so called residual stresses can cause matrix cracking and thus reduce strength [1-2]. As a consequence a lot of effort has been made to develop techniques to evaluate these stresses [1-7]. Given the main control parameters - temperature, pressure and time, we can build heat transfer models [1,4,6,7] to find the temperature distribution, which can then be coupled with cure kinetic model [1,2,4] that estimates the degree of cure (the change of chemical composition of a composite). Then with the help of a mechanistic model [2,4], one can work out the residual stresses, which can be employed in some damage/fracture criteria to assess any strength degradation. If the models are accurate enough, they can be incorporated into a cure control system to minimise any strength loss or cost [3,5,6].

Dimensional stability of laminate composites is a another major concern to composite manufacturers [8-13]. It has been observed that flat laminate may warp after curing, while for a curved laminate additional spring-in/back may also happen. These process induced deformations become more serious for larger and stiffer components used in primary structures. Consequently there is a strong demand for predictive methods that can quantify the deformation, so that they can be employed in tool design and curing process control, to eliminate or minimise part distortion.

According to Ridgard [8], there are three basic types of dimensional errors: (1) linear dimensional error, (2) intrinsic spring-back, (3) thermal mechanical distortion. Type 1 error can be easily predicted if one knows the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) of the tool, thermal lag of the tool, and the CTE and chemical shrinkage of the laminate. In general type 1 error could be easily minimised for part manufacture by matching tool CTE to part CTE. The type 2 error is controlled by the anisotropic material properties - CTE, volume shrinkage of a laminate. Given the CTE and volume shrinkage coefficient, in three directions, it is fairly easy to predict the dimensional error [10,11]. Contrary to type 1 and type 2 errors, type 3 errors are not easily amenable to quantification and analysis. This is particularly true for the type 3a error, mainly caused by ply slippage which happened before

the gelation. As far as we know, no quantitative models exist for the evaluation of the type 3a error.

In the present paper, we propose a one dimensional mathematical model of ply slippage based on springs, dampers and sliders. Some preliminary results of warpage derived from the spring-damper model will be shown in the end.

2. The Spring-Damper Slippage Model

During the cure of a laminate (see fig 1), metal tool expands much more than the laminate (for steel the CTE = 10^{-5} , while for composites, in fibre direction CTE = 0). As a result, there is a relative movement between tool and part, which leads to frictional and viscous forces. With high autoclave pressure, this will produce substantial friction force that pulls the bottom ply in the laminate. The bottom ply will in turn pull the ply just above it and so on. The viscous resin will also generate forces to resist the relative motion of adjacent plies. Such forces will act in a similar manner as the friction force to diffuse motion from bottom layer to top layer. As a consequence the bottom layer is stretched most, while the top layer is stretched least.

When the resin is fully cured, these deformations will be locked into laminate and create residual stresses. After clamping pressure is removed, the residual stresses will cause the laminate to warp towards the tool. This phenomenon is well known (see e.g. Rigards [8]), however no quantitative predictive method is available. Hence it is not possible to evaluate its contribution to the overall warpage and spring-in, nor is it possible to take any preventative measures in tool design. In this paper, we try to come up with a simple technique which allows a prediction of the amount of warpage.

As a first attempt, we confine ourselves to flat, cross-ply laminate (generalisation to curved laminate and other lay-ups can be easily achieved). We also assume that slippage is only caused by viscous and friction force. The third assumption is that the flat laminate lies symmetrically on the tool, so only half of the laminate needs to be modelled. For unsymmetrically positioned laminate, it will experience a 'shift' in thermal expansion from the centreline, which may lead to an unsymmetric spring-in. This will be addressed later. We also assume that temperature is uniform throughout the laminate and friction constant does not vary with temperature. These restrictions are mainly due to the lack of real data. If they are available, the proposed model can easily incorporate them. Viscosity effect is deemed to concentrate in an infinitely thin layer between plies, it is not considered within the ply. This is justified for 0° plies, where fibre stiffness dominates resin viscosity.

With the above assumptions, we can treat the laminate as a layered elastic body of different stiffness in the thickness direction. Between the layers there are viscous and frictional forces. The viscous force is governed by the resin viscosity coefficient, which depends on temperature, and relative velocity. The frictional force is controlled by pressure and frictional coefficient, which is the same between plies, but has a different and higher value between the bottom ply and the tool surface.

If we examine a small segment of length dl in any ply (fig 2), we will find that the internal elastic force df_e must balance the external viscous force df_v and frictional force df_f

$$df_e = df_f + df_v \quad (1)$$

From the classical laminate theory, the elastic force is given by:

$$df_e = \frac{A}{dl} \Delta u \quad (2)$$

Where A is the membrane stiffness of the ply that we are examining, Δu is the elongation or shortening of the element. This leads to the equivalent spring stiffness:

$$K = \frac{A}{dl} \quad (3)$$

The viscous force can be found as:

$$df_v = v_r \frac{\Delta v}{\Delta h} dl \quad (4)$$

where v_r is the resin viscosity, Δv is the velocity difference between the two adjacent plies. Δh is the shear layer thickness. In theory the viscous shear force is governed by:

$$\tau = v \left(\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial V_y}{\partial x} \right) \quad (6)$$

where the V_x and V_y are the velocities in the x and y directions respectively. (In our case, $V_y = 0$, only $V_x \neq 0$).

If we replace derivative $\frac{\partial V_x}{\partial y}$ by $\frac{\Delta V_x}{\Delta h}$, we arrive at equation (4). However, we do not know the correct resin thickness. Here Δh is assumed to be one tenth the ply thickness. For each ply, except the top and bottom plies, there is viscous force acting on both sides of the ply. Equation (4) gives us the equivalent damping coefficient of the damper:

$$v = \frac{v_r dl}{\Delta h} \quad (5)$$

The friction force is a bit tricky. The easier part is the modelling of the friction force between the bottom ply and the tool surface, since we have assumed sliding occurred.

$$df_f = C_f^1 p dl \quad (7)$$

where C_f^1 is the friction coefficient between the bottom ply and tool surface, P is the autoclave pressure. However for other plies the friction force can be anything between zero and

$$df_f = C_f^2 p dl \quad (8)$$

where C_f^2 is the frictional coefficient between the plies. What is even more difficult is the direction of the friction force that is controlled by the relative velocity, which is not a known priori and has to be solved

The small segment can be represented (see fig 2) as a combination of spring (for the elastic force), damper (for the viscous force) and slider (for the friction force). Further, we can replace the laminate system by a network of springs, dampers and sliders (Fig. 3). In each ply, we have (m-1) springs, and 2m dampers and sliders connected to the plies immediately above and below the current ply. Obviously when m intends to infinity, the discrete model approaches its continuum counterpart.

From this simple model we can work out the equilibrium equation for the j+1th node in the ith layer:

$$F_{j+1} - F_j + v \left(\dot{U}_{i-1}^{j+1} - \dot{U}_i^{j+1} \right) - v \left(\dot{U}_i^{j+1} - \dot{U}_{i+1}^{j+1} \right) = 0 \quad (9)$$

where u is the nodal displacement, subscript i denotes layer number, superscript denotes the nodal number, and v is the damping coefficient. $\left(\dot{}\right) = \frac{du}{dt}$

Based on the Hook's law, we have :

$$F_j = K \left(\dot{U}_i^{j+1} - \dot{U}_i^j \right) \quad F_j = K \left(\dot{U}_i^{j+2} - \dot{U}_i^{j+1} \right) \quad (10)$$

substitute the above into eqn(9), we get :

$$-2K U_i^{j+1} + K U_i^j + K U_i^{j+2} + v \dot{U}_{i-1}^{j+1} - 2v \dot{U}_i^{j+1} + v \dot{U}_{i+1}^{j+1} = 0 \quad (11)$$

the boundary and initial condition are:

$$U_i^1 = 0, U_i^j = 0, \text{ at } t = 0 \quad (12)$$

3. Solution Techniques

The equation (9) can be written in a matrix form as

$$N \dot{U} + KU = F(t) \quad (13)$$

where

$$N_{ij} = \begin{cases} -v & \text{if } i-j = m, -m \\ +2v & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}, \quad K_{ij} = \begin{cases} -k & \text{if } i-j = \pm 1 \\ +2k & \text{if } i = j \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$U = (U_{21}, U_{22}, \dots, U_{2m}, U_{31}, U_{32}, \dots, U_{nm})^T, \quad F_i(t) = f_j'(U), \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n.m$$

n is the number of plies and m is the number of nodes in each ply.

The boundary condition and initial condition are:

$$(U_{21}, U_{31}, \dots, U_{n1})^T = (0, 0, 0, \dots, 0)^T, \quad U_{i=0} = 0 \quad (14)$$

To solve the 1st order linear ordinary differential equation (13), we approximate the velocity

\dot{U}_{n+1} at time $t = t_{n+1}$, by a backward Euler Scheme:

$$\dot{U}_{n+1} = \frac{U_{n+1} - U_n}{\Delta t} \quad (15)$$

where the subscript $n+1$ and n refer to discretised time t_{n+1} and t_n .

Substitute equation (15) into (13) (at time t_{n+1}) we obtain:

$$N \frac{U_{n+1} - U_n}{\Delta t} + K U_{n+1} = F_{n+1} \quad (16)$$

which gives

$$U_{n+1} = \left(\frac{N}{\Delta t} + K \right)^{-1} \left(F_{n+1} + N \frac{U_n}{\Delta t} \right) \quad (17)$$

In theory, knowing solution at the beginning ($t=0, n=1$), we can march through time to get a solution at a given time t_n . However, equation (17) implies a very inefficient integration scheme as both N and K are very sparse matrices. A more efficient procedure is based on the following Jacobi iteration:

$$U_{n+1}^{i+1} = D_1^{-1} \left(D_1 - \frac{N}{\Delta t} - K \right) U_{n+1}^i + F_{n+1} + N \frac{U_n}{\Delta t} \quad (18)$$

where i is the iteration counter and D_1 the diagonal of $\left(\frac{N}{\Delta t} - K\right)$. Obviously the convergence of the above iteration depends on the eigen values of the matrix $\left(D_1 - \frac{N}{\Delta t} - K\right)$.

In this paper we rewrite equation (13) as:

$$KU_{n+1}^{i+1} = -N\dot{U}_{n+1}^i + F_{n+1} \quad (19)$$

where $\dot{U}_{n+1}^i = \frac{U_{n+1}^i - U_n^i}{\Delta t}$. As K has large leading diagonals, the following iteration should have better convergence property:

$$U_{n+1}^{i+1} = D_2^{-1} (D_2 - K) \left(-N\dot{U}_{n+1}^i + F_{n+1} \right) \quad (20)$$

The above scheme may diverge due to the non-smoothness of the friction force F_{n+1} , which may change sign, following a sign switch of relative velocity. Further unless sliding has happened, the magnitude of the friction can not be determined in the present problem. As a consequence, the following assumptions are made:

a) friction, subject to the sign, has a gradual decay from lower plies to upper plies.

$$f_f^i = C_d C_f p dl \quad (21)$$

where C_d is a decay factor

$$C_d = 1 - \frac{i}{n} \quad (22)$$

Such an assumption is reasonable since the driving force of the motion comes from the bottom plies and it decreases in the thickness direction. As for the sign of the friction, if $V_i^j > V_{i-1}^j, f_f^j < 0$, if $V_i^j < V_{i-1}^j, f_f^j > 0$. Further, since numerically we rarely have exactly the same velocities, if $|V_i^j - V_{i-1}^j| \leq 10^{-4} |V_i^j|, f_f^j = 0$.

b) ply kinetics is subject to constraints:

$$U_i^j \geq 0, \quad U_i^j \geq S_u U_{i-1}^{j-1}, \text{ if } U_{i-1}^j \geq S_u U_i^j \quad (23a)$$

$$V_i^j \geq S_v V_{i-1}^{j-1}, \quad V_i^j \geq S_v V_i^j, \text{ if } V_i^j \geq 0 \quad (23b)$$

$$V_i^j \leq S_v V_{i-1}^{j-1}, \quad V_i^j \leq S_v V_i^j, \text{ if } V_i^j \leq 0 \quad (23c)$$

where $0 \leq S_u, S_v \leq 1$. Equation (23a) simply ensures that more deformation should happen in plies either at the far right end or at the bottom. This is certainly what should be during slippage. Because it is difficult to envisage any shortening, all the displacements must be positive. Hence $U_i^j \geq 0$. The same arguments apply to equation (23b) and (23c).

4 Warpage Calculation

Once the deformation U_i^j is known, we can find the residual forces F_i^j in each spring as:

$$F_i^j = K_i (U_i^{j+1} - U_i^j) \quad (24)$$

from which we can calculate the bending moment M_j , by summing the bending moment through the thickness:

$$M_j = \sum_{i=1}^n F_i^j \cdot \left(\frac{n+1}{2} - i \right) t \quad (25)$$

where t is the ply thickness.

From classical laminate theory, we know (because of symmetry and only cross-ply is considered, no coupling exists)

$$\frac{d^2Y}{dx^2} = \frac{M}{D} \quad (26)$$

where y is the transverse deflection or warpage in the present case, D is the bending stiffness. Integrate the above equation twice, we arrive at:

$$y = y(0) + y'(0)x + \int_0^x \left[\int_0^x \frac{M}{D} dx \right] dx \quad (27)$$

For the current discrete case where we only know bending moment M at a finite number of points, the warpage is computed as

$$\begin{aligned} y_i &= y_0 + y'_0 X_j + \sum_{K=1}^j \left(\int_0^{X_K} \frac{M}{D} dx \right) (X_{K+1} - X_K) \\ &= y_0 + y'_0 X_j + \sum_{K=1}^j \left[\sum_{l=1}^K \frac{M_l}{D} (X_{l+1} - X_l) \right] (X_{K+1} - X_K) \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Based on the symmetry assumption made at the beginning there is no warpage at the symmetry line ($x=0$). So $y_o = y'_o = 0$. Consequently the above equation is simplified as:

$$y_j = \sum_{k=1}^j \left[\sum_{l=1}^k \frac{M_l}{D} (X_{l+1} - X_l) \right] (X_{k+1} - X_k) \quad (29)$$

5. Numerical Results and Discussions

We test the proposed theory on a simple 16 ply 0° degree laminate (3ft long). The material properties for each ply are : $E_1 = 140$ Gpa, $E_2 = 10$ Gpa, $G = 5$ Gpa, $\nu = 0.3$. The laminate is subject to autoclave pressure 80 lbsi^2 and is heated at $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 177°C , then held for two hours. Resin viscosity is taken from [14]. The frictional coefficient between plies is 5×10^{-4} as in [13], while the friction coefficient between the bottom ply and tool surface is assumed to be 5×10^{-3} . The stabilising constants in equation (23) are $S_U = S_V = 0.95$. The thermal expansion coefficient of the tool is 10^{-5} . The simulation is run between time = 0 and 60 min. Once time passes 60 mins resin viscosity suddenly rises dramatically, causing iteration to fail. Due to the limitation of space, we only show one set of results (more will be available at the conference). In Fig 4, we plot the deformed shape of an initially flat laminate at time = 60min. We can see clearly that friction plays a very important role in ply slippage. The warpage profile is reasonable, though the magnitude is quite different from test (ranging from 3~5mm at the ends). This large discrepancy is believed mainly due to the lack of realistic data for the simulation, which is particularly true for the frictional coefficient and material moduli. They are treated as constants in the analysis but in reality they should vary with time or temperature (Experiments are planned to obtain such data). Another possibility is the solution scheme adopted. It may be better to employ equation (18) instead of equation (19), or indeed any other more accurate and stable schemes.

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Fig 1 Autoclave Curing of laminate composites

Fig 2 A segment of ply and its discrete model

Fig 3 A spring, damper and slider model for ply slippage

Fig.4 Warpage of a laminate at different friction values

